

The reality of polarizing professional human resources in the Jordanian higher education institutions

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Sep 11, 2021

Revised Dec 27, 2022

Accepted Feb 1, 2023

Keywords:

Faculty members

Jordanian higher education institutions

Polarizing professional human resources

ABSTRACT

The study aimed to identify the reality of polarizing professional human resources from the point of view of academics in Jordanian higher education institutions (JHEI), following the variables: gender, educational qualification, academic qualifications, years of service, and type of institution. The study followed a descriptive-analytical approach. The study sample comprised 674 faculty members working in various institutions of the JHEI. The researcher used a questionnaire comprising 24 items as a study instrument. The study's findings revealed that the JHEI for polarizing professional human resources were ordinary. and that academic institution administrations encourage personnel to submit distinguished ideas. Also, they seek to adopt a philosophy of change as needed, while the administrations do not care about measuring the job satisfaction of employees. Periodically, it was found that JHEI encourage feedback from students to improve the quality of services and adopt modern technological means to provide their services.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Jordanian higher education institutions (JHEI) are the most important educational institutions because they serve as a forum for cultural, educational, social, and political activities. They help societies spread their cultures and achieve their future aspirations. They are productive institutions through which education is given to students. It is because universities have evolved into direct contributors to production through research and technical consulting. Distinguished higher education is the most important means of developing skills and building human capabilities required by the labor sector to accelerate integration into the global economy. Thus, it is considered a strategic investment through which the workforce is prepared and qualified as required by labor markets and national development needs. It explains higher education institutions' keen and continuous interest in developing countries in updating their programs to meet the requirements of renewable development in their societies. The establishment of JHEI came primarily to serve the community and contribute to comprehensive social development. Therefore, teaching, scientific research, and community service in various fields [1]–[10].

A university faculty member is considered one of the main pillars of the educational process because he or she plays the roles of researcher, expert, and advisor. Also, university faculty member produces scientific products that contribute to solving the problems of society and the overall development. There is a multiplicity of roles and responsibilities of a faculty member within the university [11]–[17].

The function of polarizing professional human resources represents the natural extension of the search function for the appropriate workforce. The process of polarization expresses the process of differentiation among individuals applying for a particular job in terms of their eligibility for that job. Also, it aims to put the right person in the appropriate job by achieving compatibility between the requirements and duties of the job and the qualifications of the person. The person applying for the job and the activity of polarizing professional human resources are necessary for the existence of differences. These differences co-exist between individuals' readiness, abilities, tendencies, and jobs' requirements and mental and physical characteristics [18]–[21]. Polarizing professional human resources in JHEI includes a set of issues [22]–[25].

The performance of the recruiter of professional human resources depends to a large extent on the performance of his assistants. Workers who do not have the appropriate capabilities will not carry out their work effectively, and thus the achievement of their boss will also be affected. Therefore, the management has to sort out and identify those people who are not suitable for work.

Effective selection of new employees in the organization is important because of the high costs that the organization can bear in polarizing and appointing new employees. It means they need to pay attention to selecting workers so that those expenses are not lost without achieving the goal of choosing the right employees. Proper polarization process is important to confirm the legitimacy of the selection procedure, in response to laws that provide non-discrimination and equal treatment of minorities or different races.

Due to the importance of the topic of polarizing professional human resources, many studies have been conducted on it. The study Al-Ghalayini [26] aimed to identify the relationship between polarizing professional human resources to achieve competitive advantage from the employees' viewpoints in commercial banks in the Gaza Strip. The random sample was selected to comprise 200 male and female employees working in commercial banks in the Gaza Governorate. Also, 182 questionnaires were retrieved. The researcher used the descriptive-analytical method. A questionnaire was used to collect data. The study results showed the availability of the dimensions of the process of polarization and selection of human resources in the Gaza Strip's commercial banks to a high degree. The study showed that there were no statistically significant differences between the average responses to the study sample respondents towards polarizing professional human resources due to some variables. These variables exemplify gender, age, job title, educational qualification, and specialization. There were statistically significant differences between the respondents' average responses to the study sample items towards polarizing professional human resources due to the variables: social status, years of service.

Farah [27] conducted a study aimed at identifying the foundations and methods adopted by companies operating in the field of communications in the Northern State of Sudan. These methods were for polarizing, selecting, and appointing professional human resources. They were drawing the company's attention to the role and importance of human resources in the organization and the process of evaluating the performance of employees. The study used a descriptive approach, and a questionnaire was used to collect data. The study concluded that there is a significant relationship between the simplicity of the company's recruitment procedures and the high-performance efficiency of the company's employees.

Al-Budour and Al-Nabulsi conducted a study to identify the policies for appointing effective professional human resources' employees in the Ministry of Interior, United Arab Emirates. A questionnaire was used to collect data. The study sample comprised 50 administrative employees working for the Ministry of Interior in the United Arab Emirates.

The researchers concluded that the issue of polarizing professional human resources and its prominent role in the selection of human competencies received the attention of several researchers. The study Al-Budour and Al-Nabulsi [28] and many studies dealt with the impact of polarizing and appointing professional human resources on achieving competitive advantage. Al-Ghalayini [26] and other studies dealt with the foundations and methods used by companies working in the recruitment of professional human resources. The researchers benefited from these studies in identifying the study fields, their variables, statistical methods for analyzing their results, and constructing the items, fields, and items of the questionnaire. The most important characteristic of this study lies in identifying the reality of polarizing professional human resources in JHEI from the educationalists' viewpoints, excepting the teaching staff. This issue was not addressed in this way in previous studies, to the best of our knowledge. This study enjoys uniqueness because it examines the reality of polarizing professional human resources in Jordanian universities. Besides, it explains to officials, in JHEI, the reality of the adopted policies of polarizing professional human resources and appropriate procedures for selecting competencies.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Study questions

Universities, like other institutions, seek to survive and grow in the market, and are working to develop and implement general strategies to ensure that they achieve their goals. However, universities are facing increasing challenges, including financial, local, and international competition, the pressures of diverse, changeable labor market requirements, and the pursuit of universities to achieve their missions. They are striving to achieve and sustain competitive advantages and their objectives. The challenges become more complex due to the legal and sectorial nature of higher education because what they need to comply with is relatively different from what is available to private sector institutions [29]–[33]. Universities play a leading role in the community. It is necessary to rely on the teaching staff and the employees as they are the cornerstones and the main elements in the educational learning process. The success and progress of universities primarily depend on the highly qualified teaching staff members provided by that university [34]–[37]. The main goal of the university lies in the quality of its output because the competition is intense between the various JHEI. The researcher decided to show the selection mechanisms of the faculty members in those institutions and the impact of this on the quality of their performance. They are to obtain outstanding performance in their various activities and the tasks they perform.

The problem of the study can be determined by answering the following two questions: i) What is the reality of polarizing professional human resources in JHEI from the faculty members' viewpoints? and ii) Are there statistically significant differences at the level of significance $0.05 \geq \alpha$ in the reality of polarizing professional human resources in the Jordanian JHEI from the faculty members' viewpoints? Depending on the variables (gender, academic qualification, years of service, academic qualifications, and type of institution)? Thus, the study aimed to identify: i) The reality of polarizing professional human resources in JHEI from the faculty members' viewpoints; ii) Differences between some functional and demographic variables in the reality of polarizing professional human resources in JHEI from the faculty members' viewpoints.

2.2. Study significance

The study results benefit the leaders of JHEI in identifying the policies of polarizing professional human resources and the extent of satisfaction and acceptance of those policies. They constitute a clear picture for university leaders in modifying the adopted procedures and policies to help improve the performance of the university to achieve the desired institutional excellence.

2.3. Study limitations

The limits of this study are determined by the following: i) Objective limits: The study deals with the reality of polarizing professional human resources in JHEI from the faculty members' viewpoints; ii) Human limits: faculty members in JHEI; iii) Time limits: The study was conducted during the second semester of the academic year (2020/2021); iv) Spatial boundaries: Various JHEI.

2.4. Study terms and procedural definitions

2.4.1. Polarizing professional human resources

Hammoud and Kharasha [38] defined it as all activities through which the most appropriate professional human resources are selected from candidates, for available jobs. These candidates should have the job requirements for qualifications, intellectual, in-kind, and human capabilities. It is also defined Salem and Saleh [39] as the process by which applicants are screened to ascertain who meets the job specifications and conditions, then interviewed, and eventually appointed. Zwaitif [40] defined it as the administrative process by which the candidates are divided into two teams. A team is accepted by the organization for the appointment to the vacant position and one rejected by the organization. These are the processes carried out by the organization to select the best candidates for the job.

Madhoun [41] defined it as a process of developing and revealing the candidates' qualifications. It is at the same time an opportunity that both the organization and the individual can seize to invest in the positive qualities of the candidates and promote companies. The researcher defines polarizing professional human resources as all procedures and standards through which the most appropriate and efficient professional human resources for the available jobs are selected. They should have the required job requirements in terms of creative qualifications and human intellectual capabilities. The reality of polarizing professional human resources indicates the level of procedures through which the most appropriate professional human resources are selected to work in JHEI.

2.4.2. Faculty member and Jordanian higher education institutions

A faculty member is the person who is entrusted with the educational-learning process by giving lectures to university students and using modern and multiple teaching strategies. A faculty member is considered a qualified person who holds a master's degree or more in one of the academic disciplines and performs full-time teaching duties in various institutions of higher education. In addition, the researchers define Jordanian higher education institutions procedurally as academic institutions based on providing purely academic and scientific services that include within their walls and buildings a group of students who receive different sciences through faculty members who have different academic qualifications. These institutions are affiliated to the Jordanian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research and include all public and private universities and colleges.

2.5. Study approach

The researcher used the descriptive-analytical method because of its suitability for this type of study. Study population and sample the study population comprised full-time faculty members working in various higher education institutions. The study instrument was distributed to a random sample of full-time faculty members in Jordanian universities electronically through various electronic means of communication. The number of 1000 questionnaires were retrieved from them. Table 1 shows the distribution of the sample members following the study variables.

Table 1. Distribution of study respondents' items following its variables

	Variables	The number	Percentage
Gender	Male	396	59%
	Female	278	41%
	Total	674	100%
Qualification	M.A.	286	42%
	PhD	388	58%
	Total	674	100%
Years of service	Less than 10 years	243	36%
	10-20 years	247	37%
	More than 20 years	184	27%
	Total	674	100%
Academic qualifications	Teacher	146	22%
	Assistant and Associate Professor	378	56%
	Full Professor	150	22%
	Total	674	100%
Enterprise type	Especially	288	43%
	Government	386	57%
	Total	674	100%

2.6. Study instrument

The researcher prepared a questionnaire to measure the reality of polarizing professional human resources from the faculty members' viewpoints in JHEI. This was done by referring to previous studies [26]–[28]. It was made up of two parts: i) Section one contains the initial data about the faculty members who filled out the questionnaire (gender, academic qualification, and years of service, academic qualifications, and type of institution); ii) The second section measures the reality of polarizing professional human resources in JHEI. It comprises 32 items that deal with the questions and hypotheses of the study, and the answers to these items were (strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree).

2.6.1. Instrument validity

The validity of the tool expresses the validity of the tool used to measure what it was set to measure. In this study, the validity of the tool was confirmed through two methods, which is the method of presenting the scale to a number of specialized arbitrators in order to express their opinion on the suitability and consistency of the paragraphs. The validity of the tool was also verified through the validity of the internal consistency of the scale, in order to increase the assurance of the validity of the tool. These measures are an indication of the validity of the tool; The following is an explanation of the methods that were used to verify the validity of the study tool.

a. The referees' sincerity

The questionnaire was presented in its initial form to 12 several specialized referees from several different Jordanian universities in the disciplines of curricula, teaching, scale, evaluation, administration, and educational leadership. They expressed their opinions on the appropriateness of the instrument's statements

in measuring the items. Also, they asked for making appropriate modifications, such as merging, deleting, and adding some items. A percentage 85% or higher was given as an agreement to accept the items. The questionnaire items were modified following the suggested notes and amendments, and thus the questionnaire was reformulated in its final form to include 24 items.

b. Internal consistency

The internal consistency of the study instrument items was calculated on a pilot sample comprising 30 faculty members. These members were from different Jordanian universities from the same study community, but from outside its sample. The researcher calculated the correlation coefficients between the degree of each item and the total degree of the instrument as shown in Table 2. The table shows that all probability values were less than the significance level 0.05. They indicate that the correlations are statistically significant, and therefore, the study scale and its items have good internal consistency.

Table 2. The correlation coefficient and the level of significance between each item of the instrument

No.	Correlation coefficient	Values (Sig.)	No.	Correlation coefficient	Values (Sig.)
1	*0.487	0.000	13	**0.547	0.000
2	**0.447	0.000	14	**0.496	0.000
3	**0.547	0.000	15	**0.531	0.000
4	**0.497	0.000	16	**0.556	0.000
5	**0.430	0.000	17	**0.542	0.000
6	**0.568	0.000	18	**0.436	0.000
7	**0.557	0.000	19	**0.590	0.000
8	**0.582	0.000	20	*0.520	0.000
9	**0.547	0.000	21	**0.492	0.000
10	**0.521	0.000	22	**0.448	0.000
11	*0.561	0.000	23	**0.552	0.000
12	**0.503	0.000	24	**0.509	0.000

**Correlation is D at 0.01 significance level

2.6.2. Instrument reliability

a. The Cronbach alpha method

To ensure the stability of the study tool, the Cronbach alpha coefficient was applied. It was applied to the internal consistency between the items of the scale, where the value of the Cronbach alpha coefficient among all items of the scale was (0.880). The result indicates a high level of stability for the study tool according to the Cronbach alpha method as shown in Table 3.

b. The half-split method

The researchers calculated Pearson correlation coefficient between the two halves of the test. Then, the test length was adjusted using Spearman's coefficient, as shown in Table 3. It is clear that the value and coefficient of total reliability are equal to 0.890. It this indicates that the study instrument has a high degree of reliability, which makes it suitable for applying it to the sample and trusting its results.

Table 3. The values of the reliability coefficient for the items of the study instrument as a whole

The field	Number of items	Pearson coefficient	Spearman-Brown	Cronbach alpha coefficient
The reality of polarizing professional human resources	24	0.86	0.848	0.880

2.7. Statistical processing used

The researchers reviewed the study data in preparation for its entry into the computer. It was entered into the computer by giving it certain numbers, i.e., converting the verbal answers to numerical, where the answers were given: "I strongly agree" gets 5 degrees, "I agree" gets 4 degrees, "Being neutral" gets 3 degrees, "I disagree" gets 2 degrees, and "I strongly disagree" gets 1 degree. Thus, the questionnaire measures the reality of polarizing professional human resources from the point of view of faculty members in the JHEI. Statistical treatment of the data was done by extracting arithmetic means, standard deviations, t-test, and one-way analysis of variance. The one-way ANOVA and least significant difference (LSD) tests were used to show differences between means, Cronbach reliability equation alpha, and regression analysis, using the statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS21).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This part deals with a presentation of the results reached by the researcher through the study respondents' responses to the items. These items were about the reality of polarizing professional human resources from the faculty members' viewpoints in the JHEI. The study's questions and hypotheses, and the value of the arithmetic mean of the expressions in the study instrument can be interpreted as shown in Table 4. In light of the statistical treatment of the study data, the researchers reached the following results: The first question of the study: What is the reality of polarizing professional human resources in JHEI from the faculty members' viewpoints? The arithmetic means and standard deviations of the items of the reality of polarizing professional human resources have been extracted as shown in Table 5.

Table 4. The significance of the arithmetic mean

Arithmetic means	Indication
1.00-1.79	Very low
1.80-2.59	Low
2.60-3.39	Average
3.40-4.19	High
4.20-5.00	Very high

Table 5. Arithmetic means and standard deviations of the reality of polarizing professional human resources

Rank	Item	Standard deviations	Arithmetic means	Degree
1	Everyone is given an equal opportunity to apply for vacancies.	1.23	3.74	High
2	The university uses flexible criteria categorized by job type and degree.	0.943	3.67	High
3	The criteria for polarizing professional human resources measure all areas related to the vacancy.	0.764	3.65	High
4	The process of polarizing professional human resources is carried out following sound legal procedures.	0.855	3.64	High
5	There are written administrative policies that regulate the process of polarizing professional human resources.	1.07	3.56	High
6	In its selection of cadres, the university depends on the technical and specialized skills associated with the job skills.	0.809	3.54	High
7	The Professional Human Resources Recruitment Committee comprises highly qualified and experienced persons with high management skills.	0.880	3.54	High
8	The policies used to attract professional human resources work to achieve the selection of the best available competencies to fill vacant positions.	0.958	3.50	High
9	The policies in place to attract professional human resources give priority to employees from within the university.	1.02	3.45	High
10	The policies used to attract professional human resources lead to the selection of suitable individuals for vacant positions.	0.956	3.43	High
11	The university adopts various methods in the process of polarizing talent.	0.923	3.36	Average
12	In its selection of cadres, the university relies on intellectual skills such as the ability to analyze, creativity, and innovation.	0.814	3.36	Average
13	The policies for polarizing professional human resources are implemented following well-studied scientific principles and standards.	0.608	3.34	Average
14	The process of polarizing professional human resources proceeds with transparency, openness, and clarity that increase the satisfaction and loyalty of employees.	1.15	3.30	Average
15	The policies in place to attract professional human resources prevent external recruitment.	1.25	3.26	Average
16	The policies for polarizing professional human resources in place ensure free and fair competition between candidates for positions.	1.02	3.25	Average
17	The university has a department specialized in planning professional human resources and determining annual needs.	1.01	3.24	Average
18	The university relies on its selection of cadres on administrative skills.	1.04	3.16	Average
19	The process of polarizing professional human resources is carried out following well-known and clear criteria for applicants.	0.948	3.13	Average
20	In its selection of cadres, the university relies on wasta and nepotism.	0.971	3.09	Average
21	The recommendation of co-workers is taken into account in the process of polarizing professional human resources.	0.935	3.07	Average
22	The university allows applicants to view their results in employment tests.	0.973	3.07	Average
23	The process of polarizing professional human resources and differentiating between candidates is carried out with the help of people from outside the university.	1.18	2.68	Average
24	The required job specifications are determined based on the job descriptions for the vacant positions.	1.13	2.52	Low
		0.496	3.32	

Table 5 showed that 10 items got high degree, 13 items got average degree, and only one item got low degree. These results were about the reality of polarizing professional human resources in JHEI from the faculty members' viewpoints. The scale obtained a total score with an arithmetic mean 3.32 and a standard deviation 0.496. Item 1 "Everyone is given an equal opportunity to apply for vacancies" got the highest degree with an arithmetic mean 3.67 and a standard deviation 0.943. Item 10 "The policies used to attract professional human resources lead to the selection of suitable individuals for vacant positions" obtained an average degree with an arithmetic mean 3.43 and a standard deviation 0.956. Item 24 "the required job specifications are determined based on job descriptions for vacant positions" got the lowest degree with an arithmetic mean 2.52 and a standard deviation 1.13. The total degree of the reality of polarizing professional human resources was average. It is due to the lack of sufficient attention by university administrations when selecting administrative competencies. This may be due to a large number of external interventions or perhaps due to the lack of definitively identifying the party responsible for setting policies for polarizing professional human resources. Selecting competencies impartially and objectively, away from external interference. This result agrees with the results of the studies [26]–[28] on the importance of following the process of attracting human resources in higher education institutions because of its significant impact on the quality of the educational and learning process.

The second question of the study: Are there statistically significant differences at the level of significance 0.05 in the reality of polarizing professional human resources in JHEI from the faculty members' viewpoints? These differences are about gender, academic qualification, years of service, academic qualifications, and type of institution variables. "T-test", arithmetic means, standard deviations, "P-test", the one-way ANOVA, and the LSD results indicate the differences between the averages as shown in Table 6 to Table 11.

Table 6 results showed that there were no statistically significant differences at the level of significance 0.05 in the reality of polarizing professional human resources in JHEI from the faculty members' viewpoints. The statistical significance was >0.05 , which is not statistically significant. The reasons for this are due to the lack of discrimination in appointments between males and females and the preference for the faculty members' competence. Full conviction of the selection of faculty members, males or females, competencies will inevitably lead to the university's distinction. This result is consistent with the results of study [27] in the absence of statistically significant differences in the gender variable in the process of attracting professional human resources in Jordanian higher education institutions.

Table 6. The results of the "T-test" indicate the differences in following the gender variable

Gender	The number	Arithmetic means	Standard deviations	Degrees of freedom	T value	Statistical significance
Male	396	3.22	0.457	63	-1.104	0.273
Female	278	3.35	0.548	20		

*Function at the significance level (0.05)

Table 7 results showed that there were no statistically significant differences at the level of significance $0.05 \geq \alpha$ in the reality of polarizing professional human resources in JHEI from the faculty members' viewpoints. These results followed academic qualifications variable. The statistical significance was >0.05 , which is not statistically significant. The reasons for this are due to the lack of discrimination in appointments following academic qualifications and the preference for the competence of the faculty member. Besides, full conviction of the selection of faculty members' competencies will inevitably lead to the university's distinction; This result is consistent with the results of the study [17], [23], [28] in the absence of statistically significant differences in the variable of academic qualification, whether it is a master's degree or a doctorate degree, in the process of attracting professional human resources in Jordanian higher education institutions.

Table 7. The results of the "T-test" indicate the differences in the variable of educational qualification

Qualification	The number	Arithmetic means	Standard deviations	Degrees of freedom	T value	Statistical significance
M.A.	286	3.34	0.389	35	1.399	0.166
PhD	388	3.19	0.535	48		

*Function at the significance level ($0.05 \geq \alpha$)

Table 8 shows that there were no statistically significant differences at the level of significance $0.05 \geq \alpha$ in the reality of polarizing professional human resources from faculty members' viewpoints. These differences followed years of service variable. The statistical significance was >0.05 which is not statistically

significant. The reason for this is that appointed faculty members in JHEI follow policies and standards regardless of their years of service new and old. This confirms the strong conviction of academics in the strong relationship between selection and appointment of competencies and achieving organizational excellence; This result is consistent with the results of the study [25], [26], [28] in the absence of statistically significant differences in the number of years of experience variable, in the process of attracting professional human resources in Jordanian higher education institutions.

Table 8. Arithmetic means, standard deviations, P-test results, and ANOVA test results for differences in following years of service variable

Years of service	The number	Arithmetic means	Standard deviations	Contrast source	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean squares	Calculated q value	Statistical significance
Less than 10 years	243	3.20	0.542	Between groups	0.122	2	0.061	0.258	0.773
10-20 years old	247	3.25	0.443						
More than 20 years	184	3.29	0.478	Inside groups	19.363	82	0.236		
Total	674	3.25	0.481	Total	19.485	84			

Table 9 results showed that there were statistically significant differences at the level of significance $0.05 \geq \alpha$ in the reality of polarizing professional human resources from JHEI faculty members' viewpoints. These differences followed academic qualifications variable. The statistical significance was <0.05 , which is statistically significant. To find out the source of the differences, an LSD test indicated the differences between the averages as presented in Table 10.

Table 9. Arithmetic means, standard deviations, P-test, and ANOVA test results for differences viewpoints following academic qualifications variable

Academic qualifications	The number	Arithmetic means	Standard deviations	Contrast source	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean squares	Calculated q value	Statistical significance
Teacher	146	3.34	0.389	Between groups	2.943	2	1.472	7.295	0.001
Assistant and Associate Professor	378	3.31	0.517						
Full professor	150	2.78	0.369	Inside groups	16.542	82	0.202		
Total	674	3.26	0.482	Total	19.485	84			

Table 10 shows that the differences between a teacher and a professor were in favor of the teacher with a difference of 0.56641. Also, there were differences between an assistant professor, an associate professor, and a professor to be in favor of the assistant professor and associate, with a difference of 0.54074. The reason for this is because of the faculty member's dissatisfaction with the university's promotion system, or because of personal problems he or she faces in obtaining a promotion; This result differed with the results of study [28], [30] in the presence of statistically significant differences in the variable of the academic rank of the teacher used in the process of attracting professional human resources in Jordanian higher education institutions.

Table 10. LSD exam indicates the differences following the academic qualifications variable

Academic qualifications	Teacher	Assistant and Associate Professor	Professor
Teacher			0.56641*
Assistant and Associate Professor			0.54074*
Professor	0.56641*	0.54074*	

Table 11 shows that there were statistically significant differences at the level 0.05 in the reality of polarizing professional human resources from the faculty members' viewpoints. These differences followed the type of institution variable at the statistical significance level 0.05 which is statistically significant. The differences were in favor of public universities, with a mean 3.43 versus 3.18 for private universities. The reason for this is that the policies for polarizing professional human resources in public universities are issued

by one entity, the Ministry of Higher Education. Therefore, the process of polarizing professional human resources occurs within transparent standards, unlike private universities in which the policies are determined following administrations' decisions with different standards. This result differed with the results of the study [16], [22] in the presence of statistically significant differences in the variable of the type of academic institution in the process of attracting professional human resources in Jordanian higher education institutions, while this result agreed with the results of the other studies [26], [28].

Table 11. "T-test" results indicate the differences from the faculty members' viewpoints following the institution's diversity variable

Enterprise type	The number	Arithmetic means	Standard deviations	Degrees of freedom	T value	Statistical significance
Especially	288	3.18	0.486	56	-2.318	0.023
Government	386	3.43	0.433	27		

*Function at the significance level $0.05 \geq \alpha$

4. CONCLUSION

In light of the data analysis, the study concluded that the reality of attracting professional human resources in Jordanian higher education institutions is to a medium degree. The results also showed that there were no statistically significant differences at the level of significance $0.05 \geq \alpha$ in the reality of attracting professional human resources according to the variables (gender, educational qualification, and years of service), while it was found that there were statistically significant differences according to the academic rank variable, in favor of the teacher. Assistants and head professors, there are differences according to institutional variables in favor of government institutions.

In light of the study results and objectives, the researcher recommends the following: i) Continuous development of policies to attract professional human resources in line with the needs of universities and the selection of competencies; ii) The necessity of defining the job specifications based on the job descriptions for the vacant positions; iii) Develop the competencies of employees to achieve excellence and creativity; iv) Polarizing highly qualified people and providing modern instruments to help workers do their jobs with high quality; v) Paying attention to measuring the job satisfaction of employees periodically; vi) Monitor and continuously monitor the university's facilities to improve service delivery mechanisms; vii) Subjecting service delivery operations to continuous control and improvement; viii) Conducting other studies similar to the current study in other geographical locations and with other variables.

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